

Solitary Axillary Schwannoma Mimicking a Lymph Node: A Case Study

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Abstract

Schwannoma, also known as neurilemmoma or neurinoma, is a benign, encapsulated tumor of the peripheral nerve sheath that arises from Schwann cells. It is typically a slow-growing, solitary, firm, and well-circumscribed lesion, accounting for approximately 8% of all soft tissue masses. Axillary involvement is rare ; therefore, schwannoma should be considered in the differential diagnosis of axillary and peripheral nerve masses to ensure accurate diagnosis and appropriate management. The clinical presentation may remain asymptomatic for years but can include pain, a palpable mass, or neurological symptoms, particularly in larger lesions. Imaging plays a crucial role in diagnosis, especially magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), with ultrasound serving as a useful adjunct. In this study, we report a case of axillary schwannoma presenting as a painful swelling in the left axillary region, with the definitive diagnosis established postoperatively through histopathological examination of the excised specimen.

More Information

How to cite this article: El Wassi A, Jamaledine K, Mastar H, Ouadii K, Barigou S, Benjelloun Touimi K, Hajri A, Erguibi D, Boufettal R, Rifki Jai S. Solitary Axillary Schwannoma Mimicking a Lymph Node: A Case Study. *Eur J Med Health Res*, 2026;4(2):218-22.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2026.4(2).34

Keywords:

Schwannoma,
Axillary schwannoma,
Peripheral nerve tumor,
Surgery.

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Introduction

Schwannoma, also referred to as neurinoma or neurilemmoma, is a benign tumor of the peripheral nerve sheath [1]. About 25% of all schwannomas occur in the head and neck region. They rarely occur in the axillary nerve or brachial plexus [2].

In this article we highlight an interesting case of a 64 years old patient, presenting a swelling on the left axillary region, revealed to be an axillary schwannoma instead of an adenopathy.

Case Report

A 64-year-old female patient, with a history of liver cirrhosis secondary to hepatitis C complicated by a portal hypertension, as well as a surgical intervention for an ovarian cyst 20 years ago, presented with a left axillary mass that had been evolving for two years. The mass was painful and had progressively increased in size, with no associated symptoms, particularly no sensory or motor deficits of the left upper limb. All occurring in a context of preservation of general condition.

On clinical examination, the patient was conscious, hemodynamically and respiratory stable. Physical examination of the left axillary region revealed a firm, oval and mobile mass measuring approximately 2 cm in diameter, very suggestive of axillary lymphadenopathy. Examination of the mammary glands showed no abnormalities, especially no palpable nodules or nipple discharge. The right axillary region as well as the remaining lymph node areas were normal.

Ultrasound of the left axillary soft tissues reveals an oval hypoechoic non-vascularized mass in the parietal region, containing small cystic areas, measuring 27.5 x 24 mm (Fig.1).

Figure 1: Ultrasound Image of Our Patient Showing the Axillary Mass Suggestive of a Schwannoma

The decision of surgical excision of the mass has been made. The operation was performed with the patient under local anesthesia. The incision was made at the site of the lump, followed by the complete excisional biopsy of the mass, and ended with skin closure.

The surgical specimen was well circumscribed and rounded, with a smooth external surface showing focal violaceous areas. On sectioning, it was soft in

consistency, yellowish in color, and exhibited hemorrhagic changes (Fig.2).

Figure 2: Specimen of Our Patient. The Macroscopic Appearance is Very Suggestive of a Schwannoma

Histopathological examination revealed an encapsulated tumor proliferation composed of spindle-shaped cells without cytological atypia, arranged in short fascicles. These included hypercellular dense areas with nuclear palisading (Verocay bodies) (Fig.3), alternating with hypocellular areas.

Figure 3: Microscopic View of Our Patient’s Surgical Specimen on Medium (a) and High (b) Power Magnification Showing the Palisade Architecture (Verocay bodies)

These features were associated with cystic degeneration and the presence of several nerve fibers. No signs of malignancy were identified. Immunohistochemical analysis demonstrated expression of protein S100 by the tumor cells (Fig.4). Altogether, these findings are consistent with a completely excised schwannoma.

Figure 4: Microscopic View of Our Patient’s Surgical Specimen Showing a Diffuse Expression of S100 Protein

The postoperative course was uneventful, and the patient was referred to the oncology department for follow-up and further management.

Discussion

First described by Verocay in 1908, Schwannoma, also referred to as Neurilemmoma or neurinoma, is a benign encapsulated tumor of the peripheral nervous system that develops from Schwann cells, and arises in the nerve sheath [3,4]. Schwannoma typically presents in individuals aging between 30 and 60 years old [2], with no predilection for sex or race [3].

Schwannoma is a slow growing solitary firm, well circumscribed and encapsulated round or ovoid tumor that constitutes 8% of all soft tissue masses. Although they may occur throughout the body, they most frequently involve the head and neck region, representing approximately 25% of cases, while the axillary area is of unusual occurrence, accounting for only about 5% [3,5]. The isolated form remains the most common ; however, multiple forms, referred to as schwannomatosis, may occur and involve the same segment of a limb. Schwannomas are more frequently observed in the upper limb, with a predominance of proximal locations, most commonly affecting the brachial plexus. In the lower limb, the sciatic nerve trunk or the common peroneal nerve seem to be most frequently involved. Schwannomas tend to arise preferentially on the extensor surfaces of joints, with

an anterior localization in the upper limbs and a posterior localization in the lower ones [2].

Due to its rarity, many cases of schwannoma can be missed, so it should always be considered as one of the differential diagnosis of axillary masses. Consequently, accurate diagnosis and appropriate management may be a challenge for surgeons [3].

Schwannomas often remain asymptomatic for many years prior to diagnosis [3], however, they may present with pain, a palpable mass, and/or irritative neurological symptoms can be described by the patient, especially if the lesion is large [2,4].

Ultrasound can be helpful with the diagnosis : schwannomas are typically eccentric to the nerve [6], it appears like a fusiform, solid, moderately echogenic lesions (Fig.5), sometimes containing small, well-defined cystic areas (Fig.6) , with occasionally observed posterior acoustic enhancement. It is generally avascular on Doppler mode, and contrast injection has no effect (a few cases may show a small vascular component on Doppler imaging, and contrast enhancement may also be observed rarely) [7].

Figure 5: Ultrasound Image in the Thigh of an 82-Year-Old Woman Showing a Schwannoma: Mostly Solid, Smoothly Marginated, Intramuscular Mass (Arrows) Source: [6].

Figure 6: Ultrasonography of the Left Lower Neck in a 39-Year-Old Man Showing a Schwannoma Appearing as a Heterogeneous Mass (Arrowheads) with Multiple Cystic Changes (Arrows) Source: [8]

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is an important and preferred diagnostic tool. It helps guide the diagnosis by demonstrating a well-circumscribed homogeneously enhancing, rounded or fusiform lesion aligned along the nerve. It can be eccentric to the nerve and separable from it. The schwannoma is isointense to surrounding muscles on T1-weighted images, hyperintense on T2-weighted images and enhanced with gadolinium. The “split fat sign” can be visualized : as it enlarges, the tumor maintains a surrounding rim of normal fat. Occasionally, schwannomas can present a target sign. Magnetic resonance angiography (MRA) highlights the tumor’s relations with adjacent vascular structures (Fig.7) [2,9,10].

Figure 7: Magnetic Resonance Imaging of a Patient Showing a Hyperintense Lesion along the Course of the Axillary Nerve, with a Characteristic Target Appearance Suggestive of a Schwannoma
 Source: [2]

Biopsy for histopathological examination is also an important tool for diagnosis. On HPE, schwannomas are found to contain a varying proportion of two different areas. Antoni type A areas are highly cellular and contain closely packed spindle-shaped cells forming palisades called Verocay bodies. Antoni type B areas are composed of loosely arranged spindle-shaped cells in a mucinous matrix [9].

Biopsy for histopathological examination is an important tool for diagnosis. Histologically, schwannomas are found to contain a biphasic pattern. It constitutes a varying proportion of two different areas:

- Antoni type A: highly cellular, it contains organized, closely packed spindle shaped cells forming palisades called Verocay bodies.

- Antoni type B : less cellular areas, with loosely arranged, spindle shaped cells in a mucinous matrix [4], [5].

Additionally, schwannomas are typically positive for S100 protein in immunohistochemistry [4].

Treatment of schwannoma depends on its nature - benign or malignant-, the location and size of the lesion, but also takes into consideration age and condition of the patient [3].

Complete surgical excision remains the treatment of choice for schwannomas. These lesions are typically amenable to removal since they displace adjacent fascicles without infiltrating them, thereby permitting intracapsular enucleation while preserving the nerve trunk continuity and minimizing the risk of postoperative neurological deficits [1].

Extracapsular excision can be used as well, however, comparative reports evaluating outcomes following extracapsular versus intracapsular enucleation of schwannomas indicate that intracapsular enucleation is the preferred technique, as it is associated with a lower incidence of postoperative complications [9].

It is important to note that defining the optimal margins for tumor excision can be challenging. In certain cases, complete tumor resection may necessitate sacrifice of the involved nerve. Moreover, intraoperative injury to nerve fascicles carries a substantial risk of postoperative neurological complications [9]. However, simple resection of the tumor along with its nerve of origin is sometimes possible when the lesion is located distally on a superficial sensory nerve. The prognosis is generally favorable following surgical resection [11].

Microsurgical excision carried out with the aid of intraoperative electrical stimulation is advised to enhance identification and preservation of functional motor fascicles [1].

In cases of malignant schwannoma, radiotherapy and chemotherapy may be indicated. But in most instances, surgical excision alone typically leads to complete and prompt resolution of symptoms [3].

Conclusion

The location of schwannomas in the axillary region is rarely found. It is uncommonly described in the literature, and can be considered a diagnostic and therapeutic challenge, particularly when it requires differentiating them from lymphadenopathy. However, new imaging techniques and histological studies make diagnosis easier, and resection of the tumor can lead to spectacular results.

Provenance and Peer Review

Not commissioned, externally peer reviewed.

Consent

As per international standard or university standard, patient(s) written consent has been collected and preserved by the author(s).

Ethical Approval

As per international standard or university standard written ethical approval has been collected and preserved by the author(s).

Conflict of Interests

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Source of Funding

None.

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